

Digital subcarrier multiplexing: A key enabler for cost-effective point-to-multipoint transmission

Nelson Costa¹, Carlos Castro², Marco Quagliotti³, Emilio Riccardi³, Antonio Napoli², João Pedro¹

¹Infinera, Lisbon, Portugal; ²Infinera, Munich, Germany; ³Telecom Italia Mobile, Torino, Italy

ncosta@infinera.com

Abstract—The deployment of cost- and power-efficient solutions is critical in metro-aggregation optical networks. Consequently, direct-detection based solutions have always been preferred. However, the recently proposed digital subcarrier multiplexing approach enabled by coherent detection may be a game-changer, particularly in point-to-multipoint (P2MP) scenarios.

Index Terms—Metro-aggregation, coherent-detection, digital subcarrier multiplexing

I. INTRODUCTION

Optical networks need to constantly evolve to adapt to the continuously growing demand for low latency, cost-effectiveness and capacity, which has been increasing at an average compound annual growth rate of about 30% [1]. Due to the different characteristics of each optical network segment, the optimal solution is usually segment-dependent. In this work, we focus in the network segments closer to the end-user, i.e., the access and, particularly, the metro-aggregation network segment. These network segments are usually composed of horseshoes, rings, and tree topologies, where traffic follows mainly an hub-and-spoke (H&S) traffic pattern.

Due to the very high number of existing end-nodes, cost has always been the key aspect when designing these networks. Thus, very simple optical add/drop multiplexing (OADM) structures, employing simple passive splitters and combiners – with optical filters only deployed in selected nodes of the optical network – are usually preferred. Additionally, only low capacity optical interfaces using intensity-modulation with direct-detection (IM-DD) and operating at up to 10 Gbit/s [2] are deployed. Despite being simple and cost-effective, this approach lacks flexibility and scalability and is, therefore, not future proof. A simple way to mitigate part of these limitations consists in using pluggable modules based on coherent-detection, such as the 400ZR [3]. This solution is actually already being adopted, mainly for data center interconnections (DCI). However, it is not an efficient approach when combined with H&S traffic patterns since dedicated point-to-point (P2P) connections need to be established between the end-user (leaf) and the hub nodes. Indeed, a new pair of optical interfaces need to be deployed at both end-nodes for each new connection and higher capacity than the required one needs to be set from day one to reduce the number of human interventions [4]. Moreover, it may not even be capable to scale efficiently with

the network traffic, thus requiring using several optical fiber pairs [5].

Digital subcarrier multiplexing (DSCM) – supported by advanced digital signal processing (DSP) [6] – could be a game changer for the metro-aggregation network segment. Although advanced DSP is enabled by coherent-detection only, which is costlier than the simple IM-DD solution, the potential benefits of DSCM may result in a more cost-effective end-to-end solution. Indeed, DSCM enables setting up point-to-multipoint (P2MP) connections in a simple and cost-effective manner. The P2MP approach is not new and has already been used in commercial deployments of passive optical networks [7]. When adopting P2MP in combination with DSCM, a small number of high capacity transponders (e.g., operating at 400 Gbit/s or even 800 Gbit/s) may be deployed in the hub node to establish connections with several lower capacity interfaces located at the end-nodes (e.g., supporting a minimum of 25 Gbit/s and up to 100 Gbit/s or even 200 Gbit/s assuming 16-quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM) and dual polarization), whose traffic may be aggregated using passive optics [4]. As a consequence, the number of interfaces that need to be deployed in both end-nodes, but particularly in the hub node, is significantly smaller than the one required when using IM-DD based interfaces, i.e., fewer and larger ports are allowed on hosting devices, and active aggregation equipment, such as leaf switches or aggregation routers, can be used more parsimoniously or even removed. Moreover, the network management becomes much flexible since the total capacity assigned to each node can be changed dynamically and even reassigned to a different end-node, thus enabling a software defined network (SDN) approach, which reduces the required over-provisioning and makes a much more effective use of the deployed optical infrastructure.

In this study, we will explore the advantages of the DSCM approach and expand upon the findings introduced in [8] by offering further insights into the results acquired within a real-world network scenario.

II. DIGITAL SUBCARRIER MULTIPLEXING

DSCM has an enormous potential to realize P2MP optical connections which resemble quite well the H&S traffic patterns typical of metro aggregation networks [9]. When using DSCM, a single high capacity interface creates digital virtual channels, which can be broadcast to several different leaf nodes. At the leaf node, only the relevant subcarriers (SCs) are demodulated

Fig. 1. Comparison between (a) single-carrier and (b) DSCM-based transceivers. Figure taken from [8].

Fig. 2. Measured power spectral density (PSD) of 2×100 Gbit/s leaf nodes (green and blue) received by a 400 Gbit/s hub (red). Figure taken from [9].

(and modulated). DSCM has recently become commercially available [9]. In this case, the DSCM solution consists of a single optical interface capable of transmitting up to 16 Nyquist SCs with a maximum aggregated payload of 400 Gbit/s (assuming that each SC operates at 4 GBd and is modulated using up to 16-QAM). By locking both the leaf clock and laser frequency to that of the hub node [10], it is possible to transmit the different SCs next to each other, i.e., without the risk of overlapping, thus occupying a total bandwidth of ~ 64 GHz. This solution is highlighted in Fig. 1, where up to 16 different leaf nodes could be connected (at 25 Gbit/s) to a single interface located at an hub node. Nevertheless, and to increase the flexibility of the network, 100 Gbit/s capable optical interfaces (i.e., using up to 4 SCs) are installed in each leaf node. An example of the optical spectrum that would be transmitted and received in such a scenario at the hub node is shown in Fig. 2. It is worth mentioning that, although the focus of the DSCM solution is the P2MP capability, it is still possible to use it to establish P2P connections.

As stressed, the individual SCs – from each leaf – may have different origins and, consequently, follow different optical paths to the hub node. Therefore, the DSP used at the hub node must be sufficiently robust to compensate for distortions that may be different in terms of impairments among SCs. This capability slightly increases the complexity of the DSP, but it has the advantage, among others, of significantly reducing the need for bookended transceivers in the networks, which might cause, e.g., over-provisioning. This directly impacts costs, specially taking into account that a P2MP solution enables

Fig. 3. Typical TIM metro aggregation network topology. The different symbols represent different types of nodes: hub nodes (\square), leaf nodes (\circ), and transit nodes (\circ). Figure taken from [8].

a pay-as-you-grow model [4]. Ultimately, the reduced number of transceivers results in lower power consumption, which can significantly decrease the carbon and environmental footprint of the network [12].

The flexibility enabled by DSCM, when exploited by a SDN controller aware of the dynamics of the traffic pattern, potentially enables additional savings both in terms of number of interfaces deployed and power consumption since the SCs can be reassigned to different leaf nodes throughout network operation (e.g., from residential to industrial areas during the day time and vice-versa during the night) or simply turned off when not needed [11]. Therefore, by allocating resources dynamically, i.e., optimizing the software-hardware relations, P2MP supported by DSCM networks could provide advantages in terms of resource management, transmission performance, and power efficiency. Such an architecture: i) reduces operational expenditure by lowering the number of human interventions; ii) improves the bandwidth utilization by providing the optimal bandwidth to all users; iii) helps operators in multi-year planning by using automation tools; iv) allows operators to roll out innovative technologies so that data-rate can be increased, while cost is reduced [4], [13].

III. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A typical topology scenario extracted from Telecom Italia Mobile (TIM) network has been considered in this analysis. This particular case study focuses on a horseshoe, where traffic is collected from a few leaf nodes (“aggregation nodes”) and terminated at two hubs, where one of them acts as protection. The selected topology is depicted in Fig. 3. Additional representative topologies as well as a detailed description of the approach used to obtain the results depicted in this work (e.g., the physical layer requirements for TIM’s optical link design) can be found in [8].

The optical performance (i.e., the quality of transmission (QoT) of the network) is evaluated by calculating the power levels and optical signal-to-noise ratio (OSNR) for each particular hardware configuration: number of in-line EDFAs and their placement within the network, and degree of resource sharing (i.e., link aggregation). Besides the physical limitations introduced by the optical fiber, we also consider the optical loss of the passive coupling elements (splitters and combiners) and the gain and noise figure of the optical amplifiers. For the specific network configuration depicted in Fig. 3, two

Fig. 4. OSNR margin as a function of the EDFAs count (EDFAs located at transit nodes only) for two aggregation levels and different launch powers. Left: 0 dBm, middle: 3 dBm, right: 6 dBm. Top figures correspond to A → B whereas bottom figures correspond to B → A directions of propagation.

different levels of aggregation are possible: i) aggregation level 1, where two high capacity interfaces are deployed at each hub node, one to serve the top and another one to serve the bottom branch of the optical network; ii) aggregation level 2, where a single high capacity interface is placed in each hub node to serve both branches simultaneously. In this case, one additional splitter/combiner is required at each hub node to split/aggregate the SC to each branch of the optical network, consequently usually leading to a worse QoT.

Fig. 4 shows the OSNR margin as a function of the number of EDFAs placed at the different transit nodes for three different launch power levels (the use of a booster and pre-amplifier at the hub nodes is always assumed to guarantee the required launch and received power levels). Please note that only the best solution in terms of OSNR margin for each amplifier count (i.e., best amplifier placement) is depicted. The analysis of Fig. 4 shows that there are different trade-offs regarding the relations between the number of deployed amplifiers, the aggregation level, and the target OSNR margin. Moreover, Fig. 4 also demonstrates that increasing the launch power (while still keeping the impact of nonlinearities reduced) may be better than deploying additional EDFAs, even if that penalizes the maximum achievable OSNR margin. Indeed, we find that using 3 dBm launch power allows maximizing the OSNR margin in both directions of propagation but, if 6 dBm is used instead, full aggregation is possible in both directions of propagation with an OSNR margin exceeding 1 dB and using just a single EDFA in the link.

Although the presented results focus solely on the analysis of the impact of aggregation and EDFAs count on the achievable OSNR margin, it is shown in [8] that, for the network under analysis, following a P2MP approach supported by DSCM instead of a P2P one enables cost savings exceeding 35% when considering several different traffic loads corresponding to short- as well as mid- and long-term traffic predictions.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The potential of DSCM enabled by coherent-detection and advanced DSP for cost-effective P2MP connections is discussed. DSCM significantly reduces the complexity and improves the flexibility of metro-aggregation optical network, thus providing advantages in terms of resource management, transmission performance, and power efficiency.

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